

Beekeeping for Women Empowerment in India: An Overview

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Abstract

Beekeeping is the major movement that helps rural communities to raise additional income to improve their livelihoods. An involvement conducted by the International Centre of Insect Physiology and Ecology (ICIPE) introduced modern hives through the Commercial Insect Program (CIP), trained farmers and developed a value chain to ease the marketing of honey. From farmer, group's beekeeping has become an income-generating activity for both men and women. In arrange to supply to the converse on gender roles in beekeeping, this study was undertaken to assess how commercialization of beekeeping through the CIP has influenced gender roles and women empowerment in India Results show that modern beehives introduced by ICIPE contributed significantly to the differences in gender roles among the treatment (CIP) and control group (NCIP) at the household level. Also, women in CIP were found to be significantly more empowered compared to those in the control group. These findings suggest that the participation of women in rural development programs such as CIP is possible to improve their empowerment. Therefore, a consideration of gender mainstreaming in the development and roll-out of projects is likely to empower more women.

Keywords: Gender roles, Women Empowerment, Beekeeping, Participation.

Introduction

"Education is the appearance of excellence which is
already in Men."

- Swami Vivekananda

Education is the key which that opens the door to life, develops humanity, and promotes national development. It can be a instrument for women's empowerment. It enables farm women to obtain new information and equipment necessary for humanizing and raising their responsibilities in all fields. Thus, no amounts of efforts will solve the problem, unless and until women themselves are an initiate into a thinking-reflecting-questioning-acting process. It cannot be

find until women can be hauled out of their receiving of the survival of custom to order a better deal from family and culture. Higher education provides out space in technology and the development of skills in human resources. Selection of a career or occupation of lifelong may be prejudiced by several factors such as social characteristics, family income, parental education and occupation, personal interest abilities, and higher education.

Women's present status in India is firm by the indicators like women's household decision making power, financial autonomy, freedom of movement, women's acceptance of unequal gender roles, and exposure to media and access to education. These could enable women gradually to move into every activity outside the home to gain a better status in society. Economic empowerment is a since qua and for elevating the status of women in our humanity. One possible approach towards achieving this end could be through entrepreneurship development. Empowerment of Indian women is basically related to their status in public; if a woman is economically empowered, it becomes much easier for her to become socially empowered, a sizeable percentage of rural women in India have emerged as potential entrepreneurs. They have established themselves as independent entrepreneurs.

Empowerment of women would mean equipping women to be economically self-governing and personally self-reliant, with positive self-esteem to enable them to face any complicated situation. Moreover, they should be able to contribute to the developmental activities of the country. Empowered women should be bright to join in the method of choice formation. Women empowerment is a dynamic process that consists of an awareness-attainment-consummation cycle. Again, it is a growth process that involves intellectual enlightenment, economic enrichment, and social emancipation on the part of women.

Objectives

1. To know the education among the beekeeping women in India.
2. To understand the government programs related to the beekeeping women in India.

Beekeeping Training also for Women

Training Program for Beekeeper (Male and Women)/ Farmers, wild honey collections, and beginners. The Institute is one of the premier centres for beekeeping training in the country and is familiar internationally as a beekeeping training centre for development conducted following courses with modern teaching aids:

Sr.	Name of the Training	Duration	Eligibility
1	Diploma in Beekeeping	Six months	B. Sc. (Biology/ Agri./ Forestry)
2	Certificate course in Beekeeping	One month	SSC or equivalent
3	Rock-bee handling	20 days	Honey Hunters / Tribal
4	Elementary Beekeeping	15 days	SSC or equivalent
5	Short term course in beekeeping	Five days	Hobbyist or Amateurs
6	Queen Rearing, pollination, bee pathology, CF Sheet, etc.	15 days	Persons with a background in Beekeeping / beekeepers.
7	Honey Processing	Five days.	Everyone – Not specified
8	Analysis of honey	Five days.	B.Sc. Chemistry
9	Tailor-made course	10-15 days	In-service persons of Govt. Org. / beekeeping cooperatives / NGOs

National Seminar on **Role of Women in Higher Education**

10	Management of Apis mellifera	One week	Persons with beekeeping background
11	Melittopalynology pollen & propolis collection	One week	Persons with beekeeping background
12	Training in Honey Testing Kit	One day	Anyone
13	Hobbyist training	Five days	Anyone

Source: www.kvic.org.in

Beekeeping and Honey Processing Education

Globalization of education and economy has led the University Grants Commission (UGC) to reorient and reform its policies and programs to make the current Indian Higher Education System more relevant and career-oriented with a focus on value and brilliance. It is envisaged that professionally qualified graduates with a sound knowledge of their core disciplines and expertise in a disturbed skill will have more openings in the service industry and self-employment sectors. Demand and scope for such professionally trained graduates are visible in the applied fields of almost all core disciplines and faculties in the current changing global scenario and is likely to increase in the future. The present Career Oriented Course (COC) in 'Beekeeping and Honey Processing' introduced for F.Y. Undergraduate students of Science, Commerce and an Arts faculty the academic year 2015-'16 to enhance essential employability. In 2015-16 the first time they are introducing that prospectus to the University of Mumbai. The new syllabus, emphasis on the development of entrepreneurial potential and skills amongst the students. From the academic year 2011, the University has introduced a Credit Based Semester and Grading System with continuous evaluation involving Internal and External Assessment. The syllabus is modular offering the opportunity to learners to study techniques in Ornamental fish farming theoretically, practically and experimentally by directly working with established and successful entrepreneurs in this field.

Objectives of the Course

1. To introduce the importance of Beekeeping and honey processing about entrepreneurship development.
2. To give students knowledge about various techniques of Beekeeping and honey processing and its marketing to make them self-sustainable after graduation.
3. To teach techniques of construction of Bee Hives and its maintenance.
4. To educate students about Honey production and health-related problems with Honey bees.

The Challenge

Women in India represent 29 percent of the labour force, down from 35 percent in 2004. More than half of the work done by women in India is charitable, and almost all of it is casual and undefended. Women are not well represented in most sectors, including business leaders. Though they comprise about 40 percent of agricultural labor, they control only 9 percent of land in India. Women are also pushed out of the formal financial system. Nearly half of India's women do not have a bank or savings account for their use and 60 percent of women have no expensive property to their name. It is expected then that at 17 percent, India has a lower share of women's role to the GDP than the global average of 37 percent. Also, women face great physical violence. The rate of crime against women in India stands at 53.9 percent in India. In Delhi, the capital city, 92 percent of women reported having skilled sexual or substantial violence in public places.

The Opportunity

The economic impact of achieving gender similarity in India is estimated to be US\$700 billion of added GDP by 2025. More than half of India's women don't have cell phones, and 80 percent don't use them to connect them to the internet. Globally, women make or influence 80 percent of buying decisions and control US\$20 trillion in spending. There are also social profits to empowering women. Women spend 90 percent of their income on their families, and economically empowered women boost demand, have improved and better-educated children, and raise human development levels. One in three private sector leaders reported that profits improved as a result of efforts to empower women in emerging markets. The Government of India's MUDRA scheme to support micro and small enterprises and direct benefit transfers under the Jan Dhan Yojana seeks to empower women. Women entrepreneurs explain for about 78 percent of the total number of borrowers under MUDRA. Vocational and technical training, life skills and, financial literacy programs for women to help them develop marketable skills and better decision-making abilities cannot be undertaken in a meaningful way without the involvement of industry.

Women's Economic Opportunities in India

India is one of the world's fastest-growing economies, with women mainly from the middle class increasingly entering the workforce. Urban centers like Delhi and Bangalore have seen an influx of young women from semi-urban and rural parts of the country, living alone and redefining them. However, the story of economic empowerment for women is not a particular description; it is situated in a complex set of caste, class, religious, and cultural identities. The Global Gender Gap Report by the World Economic Forum in 2009 ranked India 114th out of 134 countries for difference between men and women in the economy, politics, health, and education. On equal economic opportunities and women's participation in the labor force, India ranked 127th and 122nd, respectively. The number of women in the workforce varies from state to state: 21 percent in Delhi; 23 percent in Punjab; 65 percent in Manipur; 71 percent Chhattisgarh; 76 percent in Arunachal Pradesh. The range of women's economic opportunities between states is due to the cultural, religious, and ethnic diversity of each state. Northern states like Delhi and Punjab lag far following on gender parity actions, including the disturbing gender ratio between men and women (due to son preference and sex-selective abortion), low female literacy levels, and high rates of gender-based violence. In rural India, women's economic opportunities stay limited by social, cultural, and spiritual barriers. Most notably, legacy laws rooted in Hindu and Shariat civil codes continue to marginalize women in the household and the community. Rural women, particularly of lower caste and class, have the lowest literacy rates, and therefore cannot discuss contracts and most often engage in the unorganized sector, self-employment, and small scale industry. Self-help groups (SHGs) are a widely practiced model for social and economic mobility by NGOs and the government. SHGs provide women with the opportunity to manage loans and savings that can be used by members for unreliable needs. SHGs also are used to promote social change among the members and the community at large. Members of SHGs have used their experiences as leverage to enter other local institutions such as the Panchayat Khap. Rural, low caste and tribal women also make up 70 percent of domestic workers in India, a sector which is unregulated and unorganized. India's growing economy has allowed for many upper and middle-class women to enter the workforce, and while poor rural women have access to education and training, there is a high demand for domestic workers in urban hubs. Domestic workers are mostly illiterate, with little or no negotiating power for wage equity, and are highly vulnerable to exploitation and sexual and physical violence. There is a movement at the policy level to organize domestic workers and to create laws to regulate minimum wage, working hours, and other measures such as life and health

insurance. Currently, a national-level Taskforce on Domestic Workers has been formed that will present recommendations to the central government on better enforcement of rights for the many undocumented domestic workers in India. Women are also able to be seen in the construction sector in India, and domestic workers are mostly unorganized and rely on daily wagers. Women construction workers are regularly reduced and uneducated and have little negotiating authority. The sector is also unfettered and highly vulnerable to utilization. Women workers also earn considerably less than men, although women are the ones who do most of the tiring work like carrying bricks and other heavy materials on site. On the other end of the range, while India has one of the highest percentages of expert women in the world, those who reside in decision-making position are under three percent. Most women work in low administrative locations, and many of the young women migrating to urban centres typically work in service and retail industries, though extra and more women are inflowing the IT and other scientific sectors.

Ministry of Women Development Programme

1. Since per capita, honey consumption in India is very deprived, considering the health benefits of consuming honey, honey and bee pollen shall be integrated in mid-day meals and child nutrition programs, women health care with the support of National Institute of Nutrition, Hyderabad.
2. Honey shall be promoted as healthy nutritional food through mass media.

Conclusion

This study was undertaken to find out if the contribution of women in beekeeping led to the redistribution of gender roles and women's empowerment. Findings indicate that more women are participating in apiary cultural activities such as watering, cleaning, and management of the apiary. Also, their involvement in decision making on the acquisition of Langstroth hives, harvesting, selling, and use of honey proceeds from apiculture are contributing to their empowerment. It, therefore, seems that the CIP had a positive effect on women empowerment due to the introduction of modern beekeeping technology that addressed apiary cultural constraints that hindered women from participating in this male-dominated enterprise. Young women educated, trained, the skilled, employed, economically independent, organized, legally aware, and friendly type was reported to be more empowered. Locating the possible determinants of women empowerment, they identified basic needs fulfilment, health care, education, decision-making, economic freedom, public participation, freedom of mobility, and psychological qualities as vital traits. Training on agro-based enterprises was one such effort. The rural women, when trained to gain adequate knowledge and the skills to establish and run agro-based enterprises. Such efforts enable the rural women to become small scale entrepreneurs and to a certain extent offering employment to the fellow women folk. The present-day consumers are fond of value-added and ready to consume products that are needed for their day to day use. The rural women entrepreneurs need to be provided with the required technological and marketing knowledge so that they can produce quality products that can compete with similar such products flooded in the market from all over the world. Ultimately such efforts will help the women to increase their earnings and improve their status in society.

References

1. <https://in.one.un.org/unibf/gender-equality/>.
2. Beekeeping for Women Empowerment: Case of Commercial Insect Programme in Kitui County, Kenya Beekeeping for Women Empowerment: Case of Commercial Insect Programme in Kitui County, Kenya Peter Mburu1., Hippolyte Affognon1., Patrick Irungu, John Mburu, Suresh Raina

3. [http://www.nytimes.com/2007/11/23/world/asia/23ihtRindia.1.8451014.html!for!a!story!of!Two! Young women living Bangalore and negotiating their traditional responsibilities.](http://www.nytimes.com/2007/11/23/world/asia/23ihtRindia.1.8451014.html!for!a!story!of!Two!Young%20women%20living%20in%20Bangalore%20and%20negotiating%20their%20traditional%20responsibilities.)
4. [http://www.weforum.org/pdf/gendergap2009/India.pdf.](http://www.weforum.org/pdf/gendergap2009/India.pdf)
5. Ibid.
6. [http://www.measuredhs.com/pubs/pdf/FRIND3/14Chapter14.pdf.](http://www.measuredhs.com/pubs/pdf/FRIND3/14Chapter14.pdf)
7. [http://www.edarural.com/documents/SHGRStudy/ExecutiveRSummary.pdf.](http://www.edarural.com/documents/SHGRStudy/ExecutiveRSummary.pdf)
8. [http://deshkalindia.com/unorganisedRlabour.htm#working.](http://deshkalindia.com/unorganisedRlabour.htm#working)
9. <http://www.cathnewsindia.com/2010/04/27/govtRplansRpolicyRonRdomesticRworkers>
10. [http://www.sewaresearch.org/pdf/researches/labouring_brick_by_brick.pdf.](http://www.sewaresearch.org/pdf/researches/labouring_brick_by_brick.pdf)
11. [http://www.articlesbase.com/careers_articles/attitude_of_corporate_India_towards_working_women_1621984.html.](http://www.articlesbase.com/careers_articles/attitude_of_corporate_India_towards_working_women_1621984.html)
12. [http://mpa.ub.uni-muenchen.de/4873/1/MPRA_paper_4873.pdf.](http://mpa.ub.uni-muenchen.de/4873/1/MPRA_paper_4873.pdf)
13. [http://mu.ac.in/portal/wp-content/uploads/2016/06/4.93-Certificate-Course-in-Honey-Bee-processing-for-approval.pdf.](http://mu.ac.in/portal/wp-content/uploads/2016/06/4.93-Certificate-Course-in-Honey-Bee-processing-for-approval.pdf)
14. Report of the Beekeeping Development Committee Economic Advisory Council to the Prime Minister Government of India June 2019.
15. [www.kvic.org.in.](http://www.kvic.org.in)

Web Sources

1. <https://in.one.un.org/unibf/gender-equality/>
2. <https://www.coursehero.com/file/p6c15l0h/Rural-women-particularly-of-lower-caste-and-class-have-the-lowest-literacy/>
3. <http://www.sociologydiscussion.com/women-empowerment/how-to-empower-women-in-india-ideas-for-female-empowerment/13525>
4. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0260691716302398>